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Research article

Optimal storage sizing for indoor arena rainwater harvesting: Hydraulic simulation and economic assessment

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ABSTRACT

This study demonstrates a large roof (30,000 m²) rainwater harvesting (RWH) system in an indoor arena by considering three water demand scenarios (toilet flushing, irrigation and combined demand) via hydraulic and economic assessments. The water saving efficiency (WSE) of the RWH system for each scenario was estimated by a simulation model using historical daily rainfall data (1968–2018). Depending on the water demand, the WSE was found to be independent of tank size when the tank size exceeded 1000 m³. The results suggest that the WSE of the RWH system is highly influenced by water demand scenarios, and a storage capacity of 400–1000 m³ would be enough for the applications considered in this study. The economic analysis results further showed that depending on the water demand, the RWH system with a rainwater storage capacity of between 100 and 600 m³ was more economically beneficial due to its positive cost saving values. The results also showed that depending on the water scenarios, the unit water cost between 0.37 and 0.40 £/m³ was lower than the mains water cost (0.40 £/m³). As a result, the use of the RWH system with a tank between 400 and 600 m³ can be the most favourable range under the conditions considered in this study. Given the variations in water price, rainfall patterns and discount rates, the sensitivity analysis showed that water tariffs and discount rates play a significant role in reducing the unit water cost of the system, maintaining it lower than the mains water cost. A payback period analysis of the RWH system with a 600 m³ tank revealed that a 5% discount rate and a water price of 3 £/m³ would be enough to make the RWH system cost effective and that the capital cost could be returned within 10–11 years. This study highlights the need for preliminary sizing of a rainwater tank and an economic analysis of a large rooftop RWH system to maximise the benefits.

1. Introduction

Rainwater harvesting (RWH) has been recognised as an effective management method. RWH can provide benefits, including a supply of non-drinking water for end uses such as toilet flushing, washing machines, washing cars and watering gardens. This can reduce a building's clean water demand and water bills (Campisano et al., 2017). Rainwater collected from roof runoff is the most common type of RWH system as it requires minimum treatment and only consists of a collection area, a conveyance system and a storage tank (Ward, 2007). Imteaz et al. (2013) conducted the reliability analysis of rainwater tanks for the residential sector in four different regions of Melbourne, Australia, using the daily water balance model. They found that the RWH system was significantly correlated with annual rainfall amounts. Fulton (2018)

presented results obtained from continuous simulations of RWH systems for large hospitals in the United States and found that mains water consumption can be reduced by about 20–30%, depending on the design parameters and demand behaviour. Lani et al. (2018) assessed the hydraulic and economic performances of small- and large-scale RWH systems in commercial buildings in Malaysia for non-potable water use. The results showed that depending on the rainwater tank size, the maximum achievable reliabilities of RWH systems for the small and large commercial buildings were 93% and 100%, respectively. In addition, their economic analysis showed that depending on the water price scenarios, the optimum payback period (PBP) for larger systems was shorter (3.0–4.5 years) than that of smaller systems (6.5–10.0 years). They concluded that large commercial RWH systems can be more beneficial than small systems. A similar conclusion has been drawn elsewhere

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(Hofman-Caris et al., 2019).

Several scales of RWH systems operate in the UK, ranging from individual houses to commercial buildings for different non-potable water purposes (Fewkes, 2012). Chilton et al. (2000) investigated a prototype RWH system installed in a supermarket with a large roof of 2000 m². The results showed that the system's PBP was 12 years, with a collection efficiency of 57.4%. The results also illustrated the significant effects of rainfall trend and tank size on the capital PBP. Hills et al. (2002) demonstrated the use of reclaimed water at London's Millennium Dome, which is one of the largest in-building recycling schemes in Europe. The designed usage for toilets and urinal flushing was up to 500 m³ per day using a combination of greywater, rainwater and groundwater treated on site. The contribution of rainwater to the total water demand was 19%, with groundwater as the major water source contributing 71%. The low contribution of rainwater was due to a problem concerning storage facilities' utilisation of rainwater collected from a huge roof area of the Dome (100,000 m²). Although such a huge roof surface area can generate vast quantities of rainwater runoff during raining seasons, the area required for storage units is a constraining factor mainly due to its high capital cost. Thus, the RWH system was designed to utilise a maximum flow of 100 m³/day by estimating a rainfall of 1 mm/day. In addition to the RWH system, the technical feasibility of the recycling processes utilised at the Dome was evaluated which showed potential water savings. However, detailed information on the RWH system performance at the Dome was unavailable, hindering an evaluation of its economic viability. Concerning the water saving efficiency (WSE) and capital PBP, Ward et al. (2012) investigated the techno-economic viability of a commercial-scale RWH system installed in an office building. The analysis was conducted using empirical monitoring data for an actual building occupied by 111 people. The WSE of the RWH system was up to 87%, depending on the tank size, the system's PBP was 6–11 years. The results revealed that a commercial-scale RWH system in a large commercial building can yield more promising results.

The existing studies on the simulation-based optimization of a rainwater harvesting system and cases implemented in the UK (summarised in Tables S1 and S2) have offered some solutions to determine the optimum storage capacity for rainwater harvesting at residential or commercial buildings by taking into account optimizing variables, including cost, reliability, water saving efficiency, green roofs irrigation and runoff capture (An et al., 2015; Bocanegra-Martínez et al., 2014; Okoye et al., 2015; Ruso et al., 2019; Sample and Liu, 2014; Ward et al., 2012). However, it is often difficult to validate a global optimum for any conclusions and any applications as identifying an optimal storage size for a RWH system is highly depends on water demands, seasonal conditions, economics and infrastructure at a given geographic area (Alim et al., 2019; Semaan et al., 2020). Besides, in the UK, there has been a wider implementation of rainwater harvesting at commercial scales due to their financial benefit (Campisano et al., 2017), there is limited information for closing the implementation and investment gap in the rainwater reuse. Therefore, there is still a need to demonstrate practical ways to increase the applicability and cost-benefit of a large-scale rainwater harvesting system. This study will provide significant step

towards local and water circular solutions for further study on the impact of urban densification and climate change strategies on water resource management. This study, therefore, investigates an optimal size of the rainwater storage capacity of a RWH system in an indoor arena via daily water balance simulations and economic analysis approaches.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study area description

Filton Airfield is a suburban town and civil parish in South Gloucestershire, Bristol, South West England, United Kingdom (Fig. 1). This former airfield site, which hosted the development of the Concorde airplane in the 1960s and 1970s, will be a new urban development comprising more than 2600 new houses and 24 ha of commercial space, as well as new schools, nurseries and green spaces. There exists the three-bay Brabazon Hangar, which was built in 1946. This will be transformed into a premier live entertainment venue with a capacity about 20,000 visitors, named as YTL Arena (YTL, 2020). The total roof area of the arena is about 30,000 m²: 8500 m² (East), 13,000 m² (Centre) and 8500 m² (West).

2.2. Rainfall data collection and trend analysis

Historical daily rainfall records from 1968 to 2018 of the Filton Airfield site were obtained from the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology and Weather Underground, which is an online platform where local weather information is available (Tanguy et al., 2019; Underground, 2020). The rainfall data were collected using the nearest meteorological station to the Filton Airfield site (approx. 3 km).

The average annual rainfall and annual rainy days (i.e. >1 mm) are illustrated in Fig. 2. The annual average rainfall amount is 811 mm, and the annual average rainy days is 128 days. Two years (2000 and 2012) received significant precipitation of 1112 and 1125 mm, respectively, while in 1973 and 2010 the average annual rainfall was 569 and 584 mm, respectively. These results correspond to the annual rainy days. The years 2000 and 2012 counted 159 and 162 rainy days, respectively, while for 1973 and 2010 there were 97 and 113 rainy days, respectively. The seasonal variability of precipitation in Filton Airfield is presented in Supplementary Information (Figure S1).

The precipitation concentration index (PCI) and standard precipitation index (SPI) values were further analysed to confirm the climatic regimes (dry, normal and wet years). The PCI proposed Oliver (1980) was used to evaluate the fluctuation in rainfall amounts based on the monthly precipitation of 50 years. The SPI can provide a better understanding of qualifying rainfall variability over the selected period. From historical rainfall data and the analysed PCI and SPI values, three different years were selected to represent dry year, average year and wet year. Detail information, including equations employed for PCI and SPI calculations can be found in Supplementary Material.

Fig. 1. (a) Location of Filton Airfield and rainfall catchment and (b) Filton Airfield's development master plan and water reuse applications (YTL, 2020).

Fig. 3. The flow chart created to visualise a spreadsheet-based daily water balance model developed in this study based on the system’s inputs and outputs (i.e. supply and demand streams).

replacement costs. It has to be acknowledged that the specific system components and associated costs for this study were adopted from both RainCycle tool, which focuses on UK use (Roebuck and Ashley, 2007) and previous studies (Roebuck et al., 2011; Słyś and Stec, 2020; Wang and Zimmerman, 2015).

The net present value (NPV), standardised to British Pound Sterling (GBP, £), was calculated by the sum of present values (PV) of the cost over the project life-time (Christian Amos et al., 2016; Umaphathi et al., 2019). PV is a well-known and accepted financial term for calculating the present-day of an amount of money that is received at a future date (Linares et al., 2016). The annualised OPEX cost was then determined using capital amortisation (Christian Amos et al., 2016; Kim et al., 2017). The final unit water cost per m³ of rainwater and mains water is the sum of capital cost and annualised expenditure cost. Therefore, the optimal tank size was assumed to correspond to the maximum value of savings over the project time (£) and the minimum value of total water cost per cubic metre of water supplied (£/m³). The prices of drinking water and sewage considered in this study were based on the non-household services with a fixed cost. Equations and input parameters used for economic calculations are presented in Table S3 and Table S4, respectively.

2.6. Sensitivity analysis

The main variables in determining financial performances of the RWH system are rainfall variations (i.e., dry, wet and normal), mains water tariffs (i.e., the predicted cost) and discount rates (Lani et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2018). A sensitivity analysis was conducted to evaluate the effects of these factors on the economic feasibility of the RWH system in terms of unit water costs with variations of the storage sizes. The optimal storage capacity was determined based on the unit water cost being lower than the mains-only supply water for the same water demand scenarios.

Water and sewage tariffs were assumed to increase by 1.8% and 0.8% per year, respectively (Roebuck et al., 2011). Thus, the predicted water for the next 10 and 20 years would be 2.9 £/m³ and 3.3 £/m³, respectively. Based on this estimation, the water price ranged from 1 to 3 £/m³. In addition, three different years were selected to represent dry, wet and

normal years based on the SPI analysis results. According to the LCC approach, a discount rate of 5% was taken as the baseline (Table S4). Since specific guidance on the selection of appropriate discount rates for the adaptation of the RWH system was unavailable, three possibilities of 5%, 10%, and 15% used in previous studies were adopted for this study (Matos et al., 2015; Nnaji and Aigbavboa, 2020; Roebuck et al., 2011). In this regard, the PPB, which is the time required to recover the capital investment, was estimated by considering water tariffs (2 and 3 £/m³) and discount rates (5%, 10% and 15%).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Rainfall variations

Although the historical rainfall trend (Section 2.2) indicates that the driest and wettest years are 1973 and 2012 respectively, the PCI and SPI

Fig. 4. Variations of the precipitation concentration index (PCI) and standard precipitation index (SPI) from 1968 to 2018.

values were further analysed to confirm the climatic regimes (dry, normal and wet years). Fig. 4 shows that the PCI values ranged from a minimum value of 9.3 to a maximum value of 13. Notably, the PCI value did not exceed 16 for Filton Airfield. This result indicates Filton Airfield's homogeneous rainfall distribution with moderate seasonality. Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 4, the SPI values remained between -0.6 and 0.7 (near normal and moderately wet), indicating that Filton Airfield tends to have maintained its moist conditions, which would be more beneficial for RWH even during the dry season. Throughout the historical period considered in this study, the highest and lowest SPI values were observed in 1973 and 2012 (-0.59 and 0.69 , respectively). In addition, the SPI value for 1982 was -0.003 , which is close to the average SPI value of 0. Therefore, 1973, 1982 and 2012 were selected for dry, normal and wet years, respectively. This study conducted the analysis of the economic impacts of rainfall patterns on the RWH system using the rainfall data of those years (Section 3.4). Overall, Filton Airfield has shown a moderate rainfall trend for the last 50 years, suggesting that the impacts of rainfall changes on the performance of the RWH system would be less significant than those of the water demand scenarios. This will be conducted as a separate study in the future using real rainfall data collected within Filton Airfield.

3.2. Effects of water demand scenarios on WSE

Fig. 5(a) illustrates the impacts of the toilet flushing scenarios (TF_{YA1} , TF_{YA2} , TF_{YA3} , TF_{YA4}) on the WSE of the RWH system with the storage capacity varying from 100 to 2000 m^3 . For toilet flushing (TF_{YA1} , 22 m^3 /day), when the storage capacity exceeded 800 m^3 , the WSE of the RWH system remained constant, with a WSE of 98.3%. However, for a tank of between 400 and 800 m^3 , the WSE of the system was between 21.8% and 42% for TF_{YA3} and TF_{YA4} (108–216 m^3 /day). However, for TF_{YA2} (54 m^3 /day), when the storage size exceeded 1800 m^3 , the WSE of the RWH system was 79.8%. For irrigation, the use of rainwater for different irrigation areas was assumed: 50% and 100% for the Brabazon Park (BP, IR_{BP1} and IR_{BP2}) and the Filton Golf course (FG, IR_{FG1} and IR_{FG2}). For a tank size of less than 800 m^3 , the WSE of the system was varied from 12.7% to 42% for IR_{BP1} , showing the most sensitive to the storage capacity and followed by IR_{BP2} , IR_{FG1} and IR_{FG2} . However, when the storage size exceeded 800 m^3 , the WSE of the RWH system remained constant between 7.2% and 14.1%, depending on the water demand (580–1159 m^3 /day) for IR_{FG1} and IR_{FG2} as shown in Fig. 5 (b). Similarly, for IR_{BP1} and IR_{BP2} (151–302 m^3 /day), the WSE of the RWH system for a tank 1000 m^3 was between 25.7 and 46.1%. However, when considering the tank's infinite capacity, the WSE was between 33.7% and 67.4%, depending on the water demand. Although a higher WSE was achievable from the system with a large storage tank, such a large capacity would increase the installation costs (Umapathi et al., 2019), hence 1000 m^3 for the maximum tank size which maximises the WSE of the system for this application. For the combined use of toilet flushing and the irrigation of BP, at a threshold value of 800 m^3 , the WSE showed 24.1% and 25.6% for different ratios: 70:30 (242 m^3 /day) and 50:50 (259 m^3 /day), respectively, whereas, for the combined use of toilet flushing and the irrigation of the FG, the storage capacity exceeded 600 m^3 , the WSE was varying between 11.8% and 14.7%, depending on the water demand (499–688 m^3 /day). These results suggest that the WSE of the RWH system is highly influenced by the water demand scenarios. They further suggest that the threshold value ranged from 400 to 1000 m^3 , depending on the water demand scenarios. As a result, a storage capacity of 400–1000 m^3 can be perceived as the optimal size for all scenarios considered in this study.

The results in Fig. 5 indicate that the WSE of the RWH system for this application can be enhanced by controlling the water demand scenarios, suggesting the importance of the water demand profile for the design and operational parameters of the RWH system. Larger rainwater storage volumes result in less overflow and more yield, hence a higher WSE of the RWH system. In contrast, smaller storage tanks limit the collection

Fig. 5. Variations of water saving efficiency values as a function of storage capacity for single and combined use scenarios (a) YA toilet flushing with varying numbers of visitors (b) irrigation: BP and FG and (c) combined use: YA toilet flushing + Irrigation.

of rainwater, resulting in more overflow and less yield, hence a lower WSE of the RWH system. In this regard, the huge roof area of the arena requires a large storage tank, which could enhance the WSE of the RWH system and reduce the mains water consumption, albeit at higher capital and operational costs (Silva et al., 2015; Wang and Zimmerman, 2015). In this analysis, the WSE of the RWH system with different water demand scenarios was evaluated using the historical rainfall data. These results affirm the significance of the water use profiles in the performance of the RWH system. However, changes in future rainfall patterns due to climate change need to be considered in the design and optimization of the system, as the impacts of rainfall changes on the WSE of the RWH system are significant (Zhang et al., 2018).

3.3. Cost-effective storage sizing

To identify an optimal storage size of rainwater collected from the roof of the YA, the cost-effectiveness of the RWH system with different application scenarios was evaluated in terms of the cost savings of over 50 years and the unit water cost as a function of tank size variations (100–2000 m³). Fig. 6 shows the cost savings, which include the difference between the total costs of the mains-only supply system and the RWH system for three different applications scenarios, toilet flushing (a), irrigation (b) and a combined use (c). Positive values of cost savings correspond to a range of storage sizes, which make the RWH system economically feasible for the given scenarios.

Fig. 6(a) shows the changes in the cost savings of toilet flushing with different numbers of visitors, as the storage capacity of the RWH system increases. The cost savings of TF_{YA1} and TF_{YA2} (21.6 and 54.0 m³/day, respectively) remained negative values regardless of the tank sizes, indicating that the systems for these water demand scenarios are economically unfeasible. However, the systems can become economically viable if the water demand grows higher than 54.0 m³/day. For example, the cost savings of TF_{YA3} and TF_{YA4} were shown to be positive values at a tank size between 100 and 600 m³. However, when the tank size goes beyond 600 m³ the result shows that the RWH systems for these applications are no longer economically beneficial mainly due to the increase of the tank size thus capital cost. This indicates that for toilet flushing in the YA, RWH systems with a tank size between 100 and 600 m³ would be economically feasible. As shown in Fig. 6(b), when the collected rainwater was only used for irrigation applications (BP and FG), the cost savings of the RWH system were shown to be negative values for all tank sizes although its variation was more sensitive to the tank sizes, less than 800 m³. For irrigation scenarios, this study assumed that that irrigation activities occurred between May and October (as mentioned in Section 2.3), discharging the excess runoff into a sewer drainage system. This practice increased the OPEX costs of the RWH systems, thus illustrating the negative values of cost savings regardless of the tank sizes.

Fig. 6(c) displays the combined use of the RWH systems with different application ratios of toilet flushing to irrigation (50 TF+50IR and 70 TF+30IR). The cost savings across all four scenarios give positive values at a tank size between 100 and 600 m³, while the values turn negative at above 600 m³. This indicates that combined regular and irregular water applications could make the system more cost-effective, thus suggesting an optimal storage capacity of between 100 and 600 m³ for the RWH system at the YA.

Furthermore, Fig. 7 presents the unit rainwater costs for single and combined use scenarios (TF_{YA3&4}, 50TF_{YA4} + 50IR_{BP2&FG2}, and 70TF_{YA4} + 30IR_{BP2&FG2}) with selected storage capacity variations from 100 to 1000 m³, which are based on the results obtained from Fig. 6. The unit rainwater cost decreased gradually in tandem with an increase in the storage capacity, ranging from 100 to 200 m³, depending on water demand scenarios. After that, the unit rainwater cost rapidly increased, exceeding that of the mains-only supply water cost. For example, at 700 m³, the unit rainwater costs for across scenarios were between 0.42 and 0.45 £/m³. From these results, it can be concluded that a storage

Fig. 6. Cost savings as a function of storage capacity ranging from 100 to 2000 m³ (a) YA toilet flushing with different numbers of visitors, (b) irrigation of BP and FG and (c) combined use: YA toilet flushing + BP and FG.

Fig. 7. Harvested rainwater cost and mains-only supply cost as a function of storage capacity ranging from 100 to 1000 m³.

capacity of between 100 and 600 m³ would be enough for the RWH system in the YA to maintain the unit rainwater cost range from 0.37 to 0.40 £/m³, depending on the costs of water use scenarios, which are equal to or lower than the mains-only supply water cost (0.40 £/m³).

The results of the economic analysis conducted in this study suggest that there is a correlation between the total cost of a RWH system and the level of water consumption. This means that the water demand pattern dominates the overall economic performance of the RWH system (Ghimire et al., 2017; Hajani and Rahman, 2014; Słyś and Stec, 2020; Ward, 2007). Considering hydraulic and economic performances, consequently, the use of the RWH system with a tank size between 400 and 600 m³ for toilet flushing, coupled with the combination of toilet use and irrigation, can be the most favourable scenario under the conditions considered in this study.

3.4. Sensitivity analysis

Water prices, rainfall conditions, and discount rates are the three major factors contributing to the economic viability of RWH systems (Amos et al., 2018). A sensitive analysis was performed to assess those parameters and identify ways to further reduce the unit cost of rainwater of the RWH system compared to the unit cost of mains-only supply. Based on the results obtained from the previous section, a storage tank of 600 m³, which could maximise the WSE and maintain the unit rainwater cost lower than the mains-only supply cost calculated using a 5% discount rate and 1.05 £/m³ water price, and three water application scenarios were chosen: toilet flushing (TF_{YA4}) and combined use of toilet flushing and irrigation (50TF_{YA4} + 50IR_{BP2} and 50TF_{YA4} + 50IR_{FG2}).

Fig. 8(a) shows the sensitivity analysis of changes in water tariffs ranging from 1 to 3 £/m³. As the water tariffs increased from 1 to 3 £/m³, the mains-only supply costs increased accordingly. The baseline value in this figure represents the water tariff of 1.05 £/m³ (Table S4). The unit rainwater cost across all scenarios increased in tandem with an increase in water tariffs. At lower water price (<1.05 £/m³, baseline), the unit rainwater cost of all scenarios was slightly higher than the mains water cost, while, at higher water price (>1.05 £/m³, baseline), the unit rainwater cost remained below (0.39–1.07 £/m³) the mains water cost (0.40–1.16 £/m³) under the given conditions. The results confirm that the economic performance of RWH systems is sensitive to variations of mains water prices (Lani et al., 2018).

Furthermore, Fig. 8(b) shows how the change in the climate conditions (dry, normal and wet) affected the unit rainwater cost of each scenario. The SPI of 0 represents the average rainfall condition. When

(b)

(c)

Fig. 8. Sensitivity analysis of the rainwater cost as a function of variations of (a) water tariff (1–3 £/m³) (b) rainfall (SPI values refer to dry, normal and wet conditions) and (c) discount rate (0%–15%), considering three different application options: toilet flushing for 20,000 people and combined use of toilet flushing and irrigation.

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